

21GRD07 PlasticTrace

Deliverable 1: Summary report on the development of pristine SI traceable reference materials for SMPs (10 μm - 100 μm), representative of partially degraded/naturally aged samples in complex food and environmental matrices, and for realistic polydisperse size distributions and irregular shapes

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1 Executive Summary

The production of small microplastic particles (SMPs) as test material for the project PlasticTrace and as reference material candidates is reported in this document. Addressed are polymeric particles with sizes between 10 and 100 μm . These particles with a well characterized particle size distribution (PSD) were pressed into tablets with easy water-soluble matrix to generate samples with very small masses and particle numbers, which are stable according to transport and aging. First test materials contained polyethylene terephthalate (PET) or aged polyethylene (PE) as polymer types and were delivered to the project partners for further investigations. Tablets of the same polymer type (PET) were produced in different concentrations in order to meet the requirements of different polymer concentrations found in the environment or food contact as well as different detection methods, thermoanalytical and vibrational, and to check their limitations in the limit of detection and quantification.

SMPs are typically produced by using a cryomill (ball mill or centrifugal mill). Different size distributions of the test material were separated by sieving or filtration and characterized by particle size distribution (PSD) measurements via laser diffraction, ThermalExtractionDesorption-GasChromatography/Mass Spectrometry (TED-GC/MS), Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Raman and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Homogeneity and stability tests were carried out after ISO 17034 and ISO Guide 30:2015. As measurand for the powders the PSD was chosen and tested with using laser diffraction, whereas the measurand for the tablets was according to mass tested by Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS and for particle numbers with μ -Raman, μ -FTIR and Laser Direct Infrared (LDIR) Imaging.

The work was done in collaboration with European Commission funded projects PlasticsFatE (H2020, 965367) and POLYRSIK (H2020, 964766).

Aged PE and PET powders with broad size distribution are available as reference material at Federal institute of material research and testing (BAM, Berlin, Germany).

2 Introduction

This report describes the production and characterisation of SMP test materials for PlasticTrace.

The SMP test materials to be produced with different polymer types are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameter overview for SMP test materials (PE-polyethylene, PP-polypropylene, PET-polyethylene terephthalate, PS-polystyrene, PA-polyamide)

Parameter	Possibilities
Type of polymer	PE, PP, PET, PS, PET or PA fibres, tyre abrasion
Additives	Minimum
Aging status	Unaged, aged
Shape	Irregular, Fibres
Type of SMP	Secondary
Particle size range	100-10 μm (broad size distribution; typical sizes in environmental and food associated samples)

The idea was to develop reference material candidates, which mimic microplastic particles found in the environment. Hence, these particles should have an irregular shape and a broad size distribution. PE and PET were chosen as the first SMPs, as they are used in large numbers as packaging materials. PE in particular is the most common type of polymer found in environmental samples. PET is mostly used for drinking bottles and in textile industry as polyester fibre. With polyesters and aliphatic compounds, two polymer classes are also made available that exhibit different chemical behaviour. The density of PE is lower than water that allows particles to swim, whereas the density of PET is higher than water leading to sedimentation. Furthermore, PE is hydrophobic with PET becoming more hydrophilic. In order to guarantee the applications of the test materials for WP2, PE and PET are suitable for carrying out the tests in the different matrices as planned (PE: Drinking water, surface water, sewage sludge; PET: Drinking water, milk powder).

PE and PET particles were produced with relevant particle size distributions of 10-100 μm . According to the main application (PET: beverages, PE: films), PET particles are generated as unaged material, whereas PE was artificially degraded in a weathering chamber. Both SMP test materials were pressed as powders into tablets to achieve a suitable test material with defined mass or number of particles.

Homogeneity and stability control is absolutely mandatory in order to be able to name the developed test materials as reference materials in the future. For this purpose, homogeneity and stability tests were first done for the pristine particles and later on of the mass and number of particles within the tablets carried out after ISO 17034 and ISO Guide 30:2015 to describe the polymer content per tablet.

3 Objectives

PET test material has been supplied to the project partners as a powder and as tablets in different concentrations. More than four different concentrations were produced in order to adjust the number of particles per tablet. The aim is to generate tablets with particle numbers in the range of environmental (higher number) and/or food concentrations (lower number).

Blank tablets without polymer were also produced, shipped and tested. The production of tablets with aged PE occurred for thermoanalytical and vibrational purposes and is currently undergoing homogeneity testing according to mass at BAM before shipment.

In the next months, further polymeric powders will be produced and pressed into tablets such as LD-PE and PP. Commercially produced PET fibres (polyester) and polyamide fibres were purchased by BAM, which are typically used for textiles. These are currently characterized at BAM before they will be shipped and can be used in WP2 for sample preparation analysis and recovery tests.

It was described in the proposal that tire abrasion was also tested. At this moment of the project, we will skip that part because of time limitations and work much more on the thermoplastics. Tire wear will behave different and is black due to carbon black component, which leads to new challenges.

4 Strategy/Methodology

PET and aged PE were selected because they are chemically different materials (aliphatic, ester), which are widely used in industrial applications and can be found in environmental samples. PE has a density lower than 1 g/cm³ and is unpolar, while PET is more hydrophilic with a density around 1.4 g/cm³.

The SMPs are produced by cryo-milling and subsequent sieving to achieve particles with environmental relevant properties such as irregular shapes, broad particle size distribution and different aging states mimicking particles in nature. Compression of the powder produced in a tablet is intended to ensure a defined small number of particles and mass, which are stable for transportation/storage and against aging.

5 Results

This chapter describes the production of SMP test material from plastic pellets and/or films and the characterization of the material. Portioning by tableting is also described as well as their homogeneity control.

Special care was taken to avoid contamination with plastics. Use of plastics is as much reduced in lab as possible. The milling equipment is made of stainless-steel and used for individual polymer types only. According to the measurements, it is ensured to measure blind values before sample measurement.

5.1 Production of SMP test material by cryomilling¹

General aspects

The properties of plastics can vary, but what they all have in common is that they can only be crushed if the temperature is below the glass transition temperature of the respective polymer type. Polyolefins in particular, polyethylene and polypropylene, have a glass transition temperature of below -10 to -100 °C. If the temperature is lowered below this critical temperature, the polymer becomes stiff and brittle and is therefore easier to shred instead of being a flexible, soft material.

Two ways of cryomilling were applied to plastic granulates without additives (as much as possible) which were kindly provided by PlasticsEurope to ensure PET as standard starting material for beverages and PE as film used in food packaging. Cryomilling was performed with an oscillating ball mill with integrated nitrogen cooling (Retsch, CryoMill), and by precooling the granulates in liquid nitrogen before grinding in a centrifugal mill with ring sieve (Retsch, ZM200). A comparison can be found in the following table 2 exemplarily for PP.

Table 2: Different parameters by cryomilling in an oscillating ball mill or a centrifugal mill. (Source@BAM)

Parameter	Ball mill (CryoMill)	Centrifugal mill (ZM200)
Polymer type / Aging	Polypropylene	Polypropylene
Obtained particle size range	1-400 µm	1-400 µm
Content of particles < 10 µm	< 1 % (particle count), no significant difference	
Throughput per workday	1 g	150 g
Cooling of grinding chamber	Yes	No (starting material is pre-cooled)
Shape of particles	Flakes, irregular 	

The centrifugal mill has the advantage to mill high volumes in a short time but milling with liquid nitrogen is less effective, because the pellets were pre-cooled before grinding and transferred in the grinding chamber spoon by spoon. Times and cooling temperature may vary between different batches. On the other hand, the

¹ Abdolapur Monikh, F., Baun, A., Hartmann, N.B. et al. Exposure protocol for ecotoxicity testing of microplastics and nanoplastics. Nat Protoc 18, 3534–3564 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-023-00886-9>

cooling of ball mills during the grinding process is very effective, but the grinding vessels have a limited volume, so the throughput per day is very limited depending on the program used.

Experiments have shown that the particle size range obtained by cryomilling is independent on the type of the polymer and depends more on the parameter chosen for the milling process. There seems to be a physical limit in the lower μm range, which results in very low yields for particle sizes $< 10 \mu\text{m}$.

Polyethylene

PE is one of the most used polymers in packaging and should be announced in the project. Unfortunately, the T_g of PE is $-100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ that makes PE hardly possible to mill, because of heat release in the milling vessel produced by grinding itself. A way could be to pre-ageing the PE film before grinding to make the material already brittle. Furthermore, the generated powders will be aged and be more close-to reality.

Artificial ageing took place in a weathering chamber (Global UV Test 200, Weiss Umwelttechnik GmbH, Reiskirchen, Germany) under near-environmental conditions according to ISO 4892-3. The materials were photooxidatively damaged at an elevated temperature and constant UV-A radiation. At 40 W/m^2 , the power is similar to the near-surface irradiation output of the relevant UV spectrum. In order to accelerate the damage process compared to the environment, the temperature is up to $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Aging the PE film was done for 100 h. Afterwards the film was very brittle, and it is possible to mill the pre-aged film fragments in the ball mill to generate microplastic particles. Ball mill conditions were:

- Pre-cooling time: 15 min
- Number of cycles: 6
- Number of balls: 5
- Size of balls: 12 mm
- Milling time per cycle: 5 min
- Frequency during cycle: 25 Hz
- Cooling time between the cycles: 2 min
- Frequency during cooling times: 5 Hz

The final powder was sieved over a stainless-steel sieve with $500 \mu\text{m}$ mesh size.

Polyethylene terephthalate

PET was milled in centrifugal mill under the influence of liquid nitrogen. The ZM200 is equipped with a cyclone. The granulate is pre-cooled in liquid nitrogen for 3 min and afterwards filled in the grinding chamber spoon-by-spoon. Grinding velocity was 16000 rpm. Grinding occurred by centrifugal forces and a stainless-steel sieve with $500 \mu\text{m}$ trapezoidal holes. The bulk powder material was finally dry sieved via a sieve cascade with mesh sizes of 500, 100 and $50 \mu\text{m}$.

5.2 Size separation by dry sieving

Dry sieving is a fast plastic-free way to isolate size fractions within a certain range. Although it seems trivial it is important to regard that the yield of a certain fraction depends on the content in the feed material. This means if the content of e.g., particles smaller than $50 \mu\text{m}$ in the feed material is low, it takes a lot of feed material and sieving processes to obtain a high amount of the desired material.

Sieving means that the particles were able to pass a certain mesh size (here $< 50 \mu\text{m}$), stayed between sieves of two mesh sizes (here between 50 and $100 \mu\text{m}$) or were not able to pass a sieve with a certain mesh size (here $>100 \mu\text{m}$). Figure shows that the mesh size does not define the upper limit of particles that were able to pass but is suitable to get a chosen average particle size. Elongated particles with two dimensions smaller than mesh size can get through the sieve although the third dimension is larger than 50 or $100 \mu\text{m}$. there will be no clear cut-off in particle sizes.

By choosing the mentioned mesh sizes three PET test materials are now deliverable with a particle size distribution as shown in Figure 1.

Dry Sieving	D10	D50	D90
< 50 μm	25	44	72
50-100 μm	35	70	112
>100 μm	57	130	207

Figure 1: Particle size distribution for PET MNP test materials obtained by dry sieving with 50 and 10 μm sieves in cascade. (Source@BAM)

5.3 Characterization

The particle size is the one of the most important properties for MNP test materials. Other characterizations are performed to ensure that the material is not altered e.g., by aging, during the production process and to have reference data to determine possible changes during storage. The material itself is mainly defined by the choice of starting material which is intentionally an aged or unaged pure plastic granulate.

5.3.1 Particle size measurement by laser diffraction

Particle size measurements were done with laser diffraction by HELOS BR (Sympatec GmbH, Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Deutschland). According to the expected particle size range a fitting lens was chosen (R5 (4.5-875 μm) or R3 (0.9-175 μm)). All measurements were processed with the supplied software PAQXOS 4.1 (Sympatec GmbH) using Fraunhofer approximation. Volume distribution is presented in the following.

Figure 2: Setup for particle size measurements of dry powders with ASPIROS unit. (Source@BAM)

For dry particles the RODOS **dry dispersion** system (Figure 2) with an injector width of 4 mm and pre-pressure of 2.5 bar in combination with the micro dosing unit ASPIROS (transportation sleigh speed 100 mm/s) was applied. 50 to 100 mg of sample powder were put in a device-specific glass vial. The measurement time was 10 s.

MNP suspensions e.g., from wet sieving, were characterized with the CUVETTE50 **wet dispersion** system (Figure 3). For reference measurements 40 mL deionized water was put into the cuvette supplied with the dispersion system. After the reference measurement 10 mL of the sample suspension were added to the cuvette (total volume 50 mL). Before every measurement the sample was treated at 100% power for 20 s with the integrated ultrasonic probe. The sample was stirred at 800 U/min the whole time. The measurement time was 10 s.

Figure 3: Setup for particle size measurements of MNP suspensions. (Source@BAM)

These laser diffraction measurements were used for homogeneity and stability control measurements prior to reference material development. Measurements and evaluation occurred after ISO 17034 and ISO Guide 30:2015.

Polyethylene

300 glasses of aged PE were produced in context of reference materials and are available in BAM webshop named BAM-P201. The results and figures described in that paragraph are open to public in the BAM report. Each glass is filled with 10 mg. 10 glasses were tested with laser diffraction randomly selected with three individual aliquots 3 mg. Laser diffraction measurements was done with dry dispersion. The results are presented in Figure 4. Evaluation of the results was calculated with ANOVA (Table 3).

	Particle size	Standard deviation s	Rel. Standard deviation s
	in μm	in μm	in %
D10	17.9	0.3	1.8
D50	61.2	1.4	2.3
D90	158.6	7.5	4.7

Figure 4: Particle size distribution of aged PE powder (n=10) (Source@Report BAM-P201)

Table 3: ANOVA calculations for evaluation of homogeneity between and within the glasses (Source@Report BAM-P201)

	Source of Variation	Mean square sum (MS)	Test value (F)	Critical F-value
D10	Between Groups	0.2067	3.3286	2.3928
	Within Groups	0.0621		
D50	Between Groups	2.8240	1.7794	2.3928
	Within Groups	1.5871		
D90	Between Groups	75.4834	1.5728	2.3928
	Within Groups	47.9935		

At D50 and D90 the variation between the bottles is not significantly larger than within the bottles, which means that the samples are homogeneous.

At D10 the variation between the bottles is significantly larger than within the bottles, which is probably due to the fact that the small, statically charged particles are difficult to separate in the measuring device and larger measurement uncertainties are caused.

The particles were also checked for stability over one year (Figure 5), which looks good according to size.

Figure 5: Stability control for one year for D10, D50 and D90 of volume distribution (n=3) (Source@Report BAM-P201)

Polyethylene terephthalate

Again, laser diffraction (dry dispersion) was used for homogeneity control of 300 glasses with size distribution as measurand (Figure 6). Each glass contains 1 g of powder. The PET powder with D50: 62.3 µm was chosen as reference material candidate and is now reference material in BAM webshop, BAM-P206. All Figures and Tables in that paragraph are open access in BAM report visible in the webshop. ANOVA calculation is used for evaluation of the homogeneity (Table 4).

ANOVA results depict a homogenous distribution regarding D90 because the test value F is below the critical F-value. For the smaller particle fractions D10 and D50 the test F-value is bigger than the critical F-value, which indicates an inhomogeneous bottling. The inhomogeneities are regarded in the calculation of the uncertainty for homogeneity study u_{hom} after ISO Guide 30:2015 (Table 5) and show acceptable values.

PSD	Equivalent particle diameter in μm	Standard deviation s_x in μm	RSD in %
D10	28.58	0.27	0.94
D50	62.3	0.4	0.6
D90	107.1	1.3	1.2

Figure 6: Particle size distribution by laser diffraction of BAM-P206 (n=10) (Source@Report BAM-P206)

Table 4: ANOVA calculations for evaluation of homogeneity between and within the glasses. (Source@Report BAM-P206)

	Source of Variation	Mean square sum (MS)	Test value (F)	Critical F-value
D10	Between Groups	0.2067	3.3286	2.3928
	Within Groups	0.0621		
D50	Between Groups	2.8240	1.7794	2.3928
	Within Groups	1.5871		
D90	Between Groups	75.4834	1.5728	2.3928
	Within Groups	47.9935		

Table 5: Calculations of the maximum uncertainties for evaluation of inhomogeneity. (Source@Report BAM-P206)

PSD	D10	D50	D90
\bar{X}_{hom} in μm	28.58	62.3	107.1
$M_{between}$	0.18	0.4	1.7
M_{within}	0.02	0.1	1.8

s_r in μm	0.15	0.2	1.3
s_{bb} in μm	0.23	0.3	0.0
s_{bb} rel. in %	0.80	0.5	0.0
u'_{bb} in μm	0.05	0.08	0.4
u'_{bb} rel. in %	0.18	0.13	0.4
u_{hom}	0.28	0.4	1.4
u_{hom} rel. in %	0.97	0.7	1.3

5.3.2 FTIR-spectroscopy

FTIR spectroscopy was performed with a Nicolet 8700 equipped using a DTGS detector. Particles were measured in transmission mode embedded in KBr pellets for the bulk information or with ATR unit for surface characteristics. The spectra were recorded from 4000 to 500 cm^{-1} averaging 32 scans with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The obtained data were processed with baseline correction available with the OMNIC 9 software (Thermo Fischer Scientific, Karlsruhe, Germany). Polymer are identified according to the characteristic absorption bands giving functional groups.

Polyethylene

The spectra in Figure 7 shows characteristic peaks at 2917 and 2850 cm^{-1} (symmetric and antisymmetric valence vibration of CH_2), 1471 cm^{-1} (deformation vibration of CH_2) and 719 cm^{-1} (rocking vibration of CH_2) indicating PE. The "aged PE" was done with particles pre-aged artificially before use. An additional peak at 1720 cm^{-1} proofs the aging. This wavelength is characteristic for carboxylic groups, which were formed during the aging process.

Figure 7: Transmission-FTIR spectra of PE unaged (black) and aged (red). The spectrum on the right side presents the carboxylic peak in detail. (Source@BAM)

Polyethylene terephthalate

PET was measured in ATR-FTIR mode because no difference between surface and bulk is expected. The spectrum is presented in Figure 8 exemplarily for the PET with D50: 62 μm . Different size fractions as well as crushing with Ultra Turrax will not result in different functional groups, hence FTIR spectra.

Figure 8: ATR-FTIR spectrum of PET D50: 62 μm . (Source@Report BAM-P206)

5.3.3 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC measurements represent the phase morphology of the polymers by characteristic values as glass transition temperature T_g and melting point T_m . DSC was performed with a DSC 7020 (Seiko, THASS, Germany). The temperature program with a heating rate of 10 K/min was chosen according to the expected T_g , T_m and decomposition temperature. DSC was run with heating the sample first, cooling down and a second heating step. The second heating was used for evaluation. Intake have been 2-3 mg for each measurement.

Polyethylene

PE was heated from -100 to 180 °C. The spectrum is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: DSC spectrum of aged PE. (Source@BAM)

Polyethylene terephthalate

PET was heated from -25 to 300°C . Since the sieving process nor crushing under room temperature by Ultra Turrax does affect the phase morphology of the different PET. The spectrum of PET D50: $62\ \mu\text{m}$ is given in Figure 10 exemplarily.

Figure 10: DSC spectrum of PET D50: $62\ \mu\text{m}$. (Source@Report BAM-P206)

5.3.4 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Images of the particles were recorded with a Scanning Electron Microscope of type Zeiss Supra 40 (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) equipped with a high-resolution cathode (Schottky field emitter), an Everhart–Thornley SE detector. The particle powders were transferred onto carbon tape and the loosely bound particles were boosted with an air jet. Hence SEM pictures only show a small spot of a sample it is not representative for particle size determination (See 5.3.1).

Polyethylene

The SEM image of aged PE is shown in Figure 11 presenting the shape of the particles. The starting material of the particles has been a thin film. Accelerated voltage was 15 kV with 13 mm WD.

Figure 11: SEM image of aged PE. (Source@BAM)

Polyethylene terephthalate

Figure 12 gives a SEM image of PET D50: 62 μm. This image was done with accelerated voltage of 1 kV and 5 mm WD.

Figure 12: SEM image of PET D50: 62 µm. (Source@Report BAM-P206)

5.3.5 Thermal Extraction Desorption-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (TED-GC/MS)

TED-GC/MS measurements are carried out to ensure clear identification and mass quantification of the polymer using thermoanalytical methods. TED-GC/MS is a technique, which couples the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) with a GC/MS system. The sample is heated from 25 to 600 °C under N₂ atmosphere with a heating rate of 10 K/min for extraction of decomposition gases. These gases are collected on a solid phaser adsorber and automatically transported to the GC/MS system. There, the gases are removed with slight increase in temperature, collected in a cold injection system before separation of the different molecules via the GC column. Analysis occurs in the mass spectrometer. Detailed information can be found in literature ^{1,2,3}.

The recorded TGA curves measure the mass loss of the sample giving the decomposition temperature and give an indication about the purity of the sample. The total ion chromatogram as a result of the GC/MS run is suitable for the analysis of the decomposition products by screening for characteristic polymer marker molecules. PET marker molecules are presented exemplarily in Figure 13.

² Duemichen, E. (2019): Automated thermal extraction-desorption gas chromatography mass spectrometry: A multifunctional tool for comprehensive characterization of polymers and their degradation products. In: Journal of Chromatography A, 1592, S. 133-142

³ Eisentraut, P. (2019): Two Birds with One Stone-Fast and Simultaneous Analysis of Microplastics: Microparticles Derived from Thermoplastics and Tire Wear. In: Environ. Sci. Technol. Lett, 5, 10, doi:10.1021/acs.estlett.8b00446

Figure 13: Mass loss curve of thermogravimetric analysis (left) and total ion chromatogram of PET of TED-GC/MS measurements (right) (Source@BAM)

5.3.6 Raman microscopy

Raman microspectroscopy (μ -Raman) has been used to chemically identify PET and aged-PE particles. As vibrational spectroscopy technique, it is based on the interaction of radiation with molecular vibrations. Currently, the application of μ -Raman is widely spread to determine the polymer type (identification), the size/size distribution (quantification), and shape (characterization) of microplastics.⁴

For the analysis, a laser with excitation wavelength of 532 nm was used., and a 20X objective was used. The spectra of PET and aged-PE particles are reported in Figure 14A and 14B, respectively. The assignments of the characteristic peaks are reported in Table 6. Both the spectra have showed all the characteristic peaks as previously reported.⁵

Figure 14: Raman spectra of (A) PET and (B) aged-PE particles with all the characteristic peaks (Source@INRIM)

⁴ Ivleva (2021): Chemical Analysis of Microplastics and Nanoplastics: Challenges, Advanced Methods, and Perspectives In: Chemical Reviews, 121 (19), 11886-11936, DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemrev.1c00178

⁵ Nava (2021): Raman Spectroscopy for the Analysis of Microplastics in Aquatic Systems In: Applied Spectroscopy, 75(11), 1341-1357, DOI:10.1177/00037028211043119

Table 6: Raman shift (cm⁻¹) and peak assignment of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and aged polyethylene (Aged-PE)

Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)		Aged polyethylene (Aged-PE)	
Raman shift (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment	Raman shift (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment
3080	Aromatic C–H bonds	2883	Asymmetric methylene stretching vibration
2960	Methylene groups adjacent to oxygen atoms	2848	Symmetric methylene stretching vibration
2895	C–H bond of methylene sequences	2721	Overtone of CH ₂ –bonds
1726	Stretching C=O vibration	1440	Methylene bending vibration
1615	Ring mode 8a (in Wilson's notation)	1416	Methylene bending vibration
1290	C(O)–O stretching	1296	Methylene twisting vibration
1178	Ring in plane C–H bond and C–C stretch	1129	Symmetric C–C stretching vibration
1116	Ester C(O)–O and ethylene glycol C–C bonds	1063	Asymmetric C–C stretching vibration

5.4 Tableting

Reference material is needed for methods validation of the detection methods, but also for sample preparation and sampling of microplastic analysis. Especially vibrational methods require very low number of particles. Such low numbers (ng) cannot be weight with an analytical balance. The uncertainty is too high. The idea is to prepare a big batch of polymeric particles and a water-soluble matrix and do a solid phase dilution. If the particles are homogeneously distributed in the whole batch, it should be possible to press tablets with very low mass or number of particles. Additionally, the tablet leads to transport stability of the particles and prevent aging due to embedding.

5.4.1 Processing of tablets

For tableting it is necessary to get a water-soluble and homogeneous matrix. Lactose and polyethylene glycol (PEG) were chosen as the tablet matrix and for the production of blank value tablets without polymer content. PET or aged PE was added to lactose and PEG to get tablets with a defined mass and particle number of polymers. The production of a homogeneous tableting starting mixture is achieved by adding the individual components step by step and in between homogenizing them in several steps with a tumble mixer. Each type of tablets contains only one type of polymer.

Tableting is done with the TDP 5 Desktop Tablet Press (LFA Machines Oxford LTD, United Kingdom) by hand mode to ensure that the individual tablets are visually identical and have no breaking edges. Control weighing is also carried out in 10-20% of the tablets to ensure that there is no excessive fluctuation in the tablet mass. To prevent the tablets from flaking off, the stamp is cleaned and dried at regular intervals. The tableting mixture and the finished tablets are stored in a vacuum drying cabinet. Figure 15 shows the tablet press and some tablets. For the tablets, 6 tablets were bottled in a glass for the blank value tablets and one tablet for the polymer-containing tablets.

Figure 15: Picture of tablet press (left) and tablets containing polymer (right)

5.4.2 Homogeneity control of tablets containing PET

Whenever developing a reference material or a representative test material homogeneity control is mandatory to guaranty that each sample is similar to the other one of the same Batch. The homogeneity control is provided to a measurand, which is characteristic for a property. We have chosen the mass as measurand for the mass-based methods Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS and the size/size distribution for vibrational microscopy techniques such as Raman, μ -FTIR and LDIR microscopy. The homogeneity testing of the tablets is carried out after the tablets were filtered using a standard operating procedure developed for this purpose (see Annex 7.1). Different Batches with different concentrations of PET were prepared. Batch 1 was prepared for mass-based methods only. The idea of batch 2 to 4 is to go down with the particle number to see the limit of detection for μ FTIR, LDIR and μ Raman. The theoretical calculated mass per tablet within the different Batches is:

Batch 1: 400 μ g

Batch 2: 20 μ g

Batch 3: 0.2 μ g

The PET particles were first characterized according to polymer type, shape and size distribution to understand the expected size distribution in the final tablets. The tablets containing PET particles in various concentrations were analyzed using several ISO-approved detection methods aimed at demonstrating homogeneity in terms of mass and particle number. The following sections demonstrate the results of the PET particle characterization, the homogeneity and stability control and further information on particle mass and number to support the suitability of the product as reference material fulfilling the criteria of QdD for MP method validation.

Gravimetric measurements

First indication of homogeneity is presented in Figure 16. 10 tablets of Batch 1 and Batch 2 were filtered over a 5 μm pore sized filter (stainless steel, 9 mm in diameter) and analyzed by TGA. The measurements can be used to calculate the PET polymer mass within the tablets. Lactose and PEG6000 decompose at lower temperatures than PET during the heating, hence the mass loss between 330 and 480°C can be assumed as mass loss of PET. The theoretical PET mass of 400 μg (Batch1) and 18.6 μg (Batch 2) is matching well with the calculated mean masses (n=10) by TGA measurements: $m(\text{Batch1})=398.0 \pm 47.3 \mu\text{g}$ and $m(\text{Batch2})=19.6 \pm 1.8 \mu\text{g}$. The standard deviation for both Batches is approx. 8-12%. It should be noticed that the uncertainty of the TGA itself is given with 2 μg from the manufacturer.

Figure 16: PET masses per tablet determined by TGA for Batch 1 (left) and Batch 2 (right); n=10

Thermoanalytical methods GC/MS based methods

The reference material is to be known for validation of microplastic detection methods. In accordance with our QbD approach and the ISO document ISO/DIS 16094-2, other mass-based methods are selected for the measurements as informative information to support the TGA as a homogeneity control and to give reference values for the detection methods probably used. 17 PET-containing tablets with the concentration of batch 1 were each measured with Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS with direct sample preparation (weighing in a pyrolysis vessel directly). Further measurements were carried out with 10 tablets that were analysed after derivatization of the PET particles.

Figure 17: PET masses per tablet detected with Py-GC/MS derivatized and non-derivatized as well as TED-GC/MS. The table gives mean values, STD and rel STD in numbers. (PET-polyethylene terephthalate, TED-GC/MS-Thermal-extraction/desorption-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry, Py-GC/MS-Pyrolysis-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry, STD-standard deviation, rel STD-relative standard deviation)

The results are presented in Figure 17. All 44 measurements of Batch1 are in good relation to each other with 422.3 µg as mean value and 88.7 µg (21.0%) standard deviation (STD) (rel STD) and totally inline to the reference value detected by homogeneity control with TGA as 398.0 +/- 47.3 µg (see section 3.2). It is obvious that Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS show quite comparable mean values with 448.9 and 431.3 µg both slightly overestimating the reference value. The STD of TED-GC/MS is lower than the one of Py-GC/MS. The derivatized PET particles detected in Py-GC/MS gives a slight underestimation compared to the reference value indicating that maybe not all particles are reached for derivatization, hence will not be detected when using dimethyl terephthalate as quantifier.

The concentration of Batch2 is diluted by a factor of 30 compared to Batch1 to achieve a concentration with lower mass and particle numbers being more realistic according to mass/numbers found in food context. Again 10 tablets each were analysed with Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS with direct pyrolysis and further 10 tablets with Py-GC/MS after derivatization. All three methods show similar mean values (Figure 6) with an average of 17.1 +/- 5.7 µm (33.1%) that corresponds to the TGA reference value of 19.8 +/- 1.8 µg. The Py-GC/MS measurements are very equal in mass and STD, while the STD of the TED-GC/MS measurements is quite high with 48.6%.

Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS show the same masses as determined by TGA. Higher masses seem to overestimate, while smaller masses near the limit of detection are within the reference value or are slightly underestimated. Overall, the masses and the STD are in the same range and correspond well with theoretical values and the reference that makes the PET tablets a valuable product for usage in method validation for MP detection methods supporting EU directives and monitoring campaigns to measure true values.

Stability control (Fig.18) was done on 2 to 3 tablets after 6 or 12 months. No changes in mass could be observed. Batch 3 was not analysed for mass because the concentration is very small and most likely below the detection limits for the thermal analytical methods.

Figure 18: Stability control tests of PET mass per tablet calculated by Py-GC/MS, TED-GC/MS and TGA over a time span of 0-6 M and 0-12M for Batch 1 and Batch 2, respectively. The red lines in both graphs indicate the theoretical mass.

Spectroscopic methods

The tablets containing PET were also analysed for particle numbers and size distributions as this is an important pillar for supplementing the masses. Batch 1 was not analysed according to the particle number since the high mass already indicates that the number of particles would be too many and too time consuming. Tablets with the PET concentration of Batch 2 and Batch 3 were analysed by μ -Raman and μ -FTIR. As the detection limit for μ -FTIR is limited for smaller particles, μ -FTIR analysis according to ISO/DIS 16094-2 was only performed for particles larger than 20 μ m. A similar comparison was done for tablets containing PET with the lowest concentration Batch 3. The results can be seen in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Comparison of particle numbers of Batch 2 and 3 detected with μ -FTIR and μ -Raman, n=10, all measurements are done in the same laboratory(μ -FTIR – FourierTransform InfraRed microscopy, μ -Raman - Raman microscopy)

The particle numbers counted with μ -Raman and μ -FTIR are similar for particle sizes larger than 50 μm . In contrast, μ -FTIR detects 56% (Batch 2) and 55% (Batch 3) PET particles less than μ -Raman. Although the total number of particles has been reduced from 1759 ($n=10$, μ -Raman, 5-500 μm) for Batch 2 to 151 particles for Batch 3 ($n=10$, μ -Raman, 5-500 μm) it is obvious that the behaviour is similar. The similar behaviour independent of the concentration indicates a systematic measurement error based on different measurement methods. All size distributions determined by microscopy show the highest standard deviations for very small or very large sizes (5-10 and 100-500 μm), while the lowest standard deviations are recorded for the size fraction of 20-50 μm . This is probably due to the number of particles per size class. From a statistical point of view, it is easier to distribute more particles of the same size homogeneously from tablet to tablet than fewer particles. The presence or absence of individual particles in a tablet changes the relative standard deviation much more when the total number of particles in this size class is very small.

For a proper comparison on Batch 2, four laboratories additionally measured 10 tablets with different μ -FTIR modalities, i.e. single spot measurements, FPA-FTIR and LD-IR, while three different labs measured the particle numbers and sizes with μ -Raman.

As indicated in Fig. 20, the total particle counts using different micro-FTIR modalities and instrumentations confirm a similar value for the cumulative particle number and the respective size ranges, while further highlights the spatial resolution limit for infrared characterization below 50 μm in respect with Raman analysis. Even applying an HQI threshold below 60%, which might be reasonable for the characterization of a pure pristine materials, the number of detected particles in the 50-20 μm size range for microFTIR significantly differ from the Raman counting in this size range. It can be concluded that an accurate quantification of microplastics below a 50 micron can be only guaranteed by a Raman characterization.

Figure 20: Comparison of particle numbers of Batch 2 with different μ -FTIR modalities, i.e. single spot measurements, FPA-FTIR and LD-IR; each lab measured $n=10$ tablets of Batch 2.

A μ -Raman analysis on Batch 2 was also performed by three different laboratories on 8 to 10 tablets. Individual particle numbers can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7: Batch 2 - Detected particle numbers of PET containing tablets determined by μ -Raman analysis from three different laboratories (sorted by size)

	Tablet number	5-10 μm	10-20 μm	20-50 μm	50-100 μm	100-500 μm	Sum
NQAC Vittel	1	66	245	882	379	57	1629
	2	32	239	856	386	79	1592
	3	37	241	814	374	81	1547
	4	128	392	931	342	41	1834
	5	110	351	899	349	67	1776
	6	151	366	964	392	67	1940
	7	147	359	851	312	72	1741
	8	119	384	802	324	84	1713
	9	147	357	965	397	80	1946
	10	170	369	927	357	52	1875
INRIM	1	207	361	855	387	70	1880
	2	146	302	766	359	78	1651
	3	173	329	784	363	67	1716
	4	143	292	831	296	54	1616
	5	279	337	777	379	92	1864
	6	89	263	920	397	68	1737
	7	233	428	1017	297	55	2030
	8	257	405	943	329	50	1984
LNE	1	180	339	905	311	50	1785
	2	227	414	926	272	26	1865
	3	170	318	849	279	54	1670
	4	166	331	749	280	51	1577
	5	209	387	923	254	26	1799
	6	124	174	905	336	43	1582
	7	231	393	986	291	3	1904
	8	278	358	970	376	71	2053
	9	209	361	790	188	13	1561
	10	147	309	785	262	33	1536
Mean value		163	336	878	331	57	1764
STD		65	60	75	53	22	155
Rel STD / %		39.6	17.9	8.5	15.9	38.7	8.8

Figure 21 presents and compares the PET tablet particle numbers counted and sorted for the size fractions 1-5, 5-10, 10-20, 20-50, 50-100 and 100-500 μm to the laser diffraction results of the originally used PET powder.

The particle numbers in the individual size classes match well within and between the labs. The mean total particle number (n=28) in the tablets with a size between 20 and 500 μm is 1,764 +/- 155 (8.8%). This corresponds with the results of the laser diffraction. A direct comparison of the relative number of particles per size class determined by μ-Raman and the integrated area of the size classes determined by laser diffraction shows good agreement (Table 8). Almost 50% of all particles are in the size range of 20-50 μm. A shift towards smaller particles can be observed for μ-Raman. While laser diffraction shows a further 44 % in the size range of 50-100 μm, the number of particles counted with μ-Raman in this size class is only 19 %, but with higher proportions in the smaller size classes 10-20 and 5-10 μm.

Figure 21: Lab-to-lab comparison of PET particle numbers per tablet detected by μ-Raman of three different partner

Table 4: Comparison of integrated areas of different size fractions determined with laser diffraction to mean values of all partners of particle numbers per fraction and over all 28 tablets measured

	Size fraction	μm	5-10	10-20	20-50	50-100	100-500
Laser diffraction	Ratio	%	0.5	4.4	49.1	44.4	1.7
	integrated area						
μ-Raman	Ratio	%	9.3	19.0	49.7	18.8	3.2
	integrated area (mean all partners)						

Matrix contamination

It is obvious that lab Blanks need to be taken for accurate measurements as part of QA/QC. However, it is equally important the analysis of the matrix as possible source for contamination. Therefore, tablets were produced as Blanks containing lactose and PEG without additional polymer. These tablets were tested in different labs for particle number and mass after running through the entire filtration process as the PET containing tablets. As a result, no thermoplastic polymers could be detected using thermos-analytical methods. No particles are present or more likely the mass is below the detection limit of the devices.

In contrast, six different types of polymer particles were detected in number-based approaches. A summary of the results is given in Figure 22 together with a Raman/SEM image of one filter after Blank tablet procedure. Polymers found are: Polyethylene, polypropylene, polystyrene, PET, polyamide and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE). The number of particles that could be detected is very low compared to 1759 PET particles (average) in Batch 2. Hence, the matrix is sufficient clean to be used for the production of reference materials. If the number of particles will be decreased like in Batch 3, the contamination becomes more relevant. It should be noticed that the polymer concentration measured in the Blank tablets shows the matrix contamination as well as any possible contamination during the sample production, storage, transportation, sample preparation (filtration) and measuring of the filter itself. Overall, the contamination was lower than the LOD for PET measurements in all laboratories, therefore it can be considered acceptable for this purpose. It is also very likely that μ -Raman detects more particles than μ -FTIR due the Raman higher spatial resolution which explains the PS particles that are not found in μ -FTIR. The particles are more likely smaller than 20 μ m. PTFE can also only be detected in μ -Raman which gives the impression that the particles are again smaller than 20 μ m and that somewhere in the sample preparation process a sealing made of PTFE was used.

Figure 22: Blank tablet filter SEM image (left) and summary of contamination found in Blank tablets determined by μ -Raman and μ -FTIR (n=8/n=7) (right) (PE -polyethylene, PP - polypropylene, PS - polystyrene, PET – polyethylene terephthalate, PA – polyamide, PTFE - polytetrafluoroethylene)

6 Conclusions

Tiny plastic particles mixed with sugar lactose by solid phase dilution and pressed into tablets is a suitable way to produce many reference materials in short time that contain defined microplastics homogeneously distributed. Furthermore, the samples are stable over time for storage and transportation. Well-done mixture processing lead to homogenization that can be diluted down to smaller microplastic particle numbers and masses overcoming the challenges of individual weighing with analytical balances.

As there is only one polymer per tablet, homogeneity testing is possible using complementary methods underlying the true mass and particle numbers. Samples with polymer mix can be easily prepared in any laboratory according to requirements and wishes. Only tablets with different polymer types need to be drawn over the same filter.

The principle can be transferred to microplastic particles of other polymer types that are in the same size range which enables the diverse availability of microplastic reference material for sample preparation and detection. Production of microplastic sized powders is possible with cryo-milling and subsequent sieving. Difficulties can be seen, when using highly charged film fragments as polymer material. Homogeneity testing was partially affected in Aged-PE tablets as indicated by a standard deviation of about 40% for cumulative particle numbers in the size range 500-5 micron. Obviously, it is more difficult to distribute the film fragments homogeneously by solid phase dilution which they stuck together. The next step is to add commercially available LD-PE particles (10-100 μm) with a stone-like structure to the tablets. This sounds more promising at the moment because the structure is similar to the PET (Figure 23).

Figure 23: SEM image of LD-PE (low density polyethylene) (Source@BAM)

Tablet production is a promising tool to produce reference materials for microplastic detection according to mass and particle number, however lots of challenges are still open. The uncertainties between the different labs and techniques are not fully understood, especially at the small micrometer level (below 20 micron), and need further investigations. Uncertainties can occur due to particle number variations in the tablets itself, by the sample preparations or detection set up. Different brands of the same technique, different operators,

different filters or even different software for detection can lead to high variations in particle numbers and masses. The PlasticTrace project can only be a first guidance to accurate and precise microplastic measurements with validated and robust detection methods that are the basis for any true understanding on microplastic occurrence, entry pathways or sinks and even monitoring that is demanded in the drinking water directive of European Commission.

7 Annex

7.1 SOP Filtration of SMPs

SOP FILTRATION OF NANO- AND MICROPLASTIC PARTICLES FROM LIQUID SOLUTION

1. Procedure details

Procedure author	PlasticTrace, WG1
Creation	03/01/2023
Revision Date/Revised by	28/02/2023
Responsible persons	Paul-Tiberiu Miclea, Korinna Altmann, Yosri Wiesner
Digital file name	
Digital file location	

2. Process or experiment description

This standard operating procedure (SOP) has been developed for liquid filtration of solid plastic particles in micro (1-1000 μm) and nano ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$) size ranges [1]. The samples are plastic particles dispersed in solid matrix or liquid. The SOP is especially developed as sample preparation step for quantitative microplastics analysis for spectroscopic vibrational and thermoanalytical methods working plastic-free, and hence reducing contamination.

3. References

- [1] C. Hagendorf, S. Richter, M. Krause, J. Bauer, P. -T. Miclea, U. Braun, et al, in ICSEWEN19: <https://opus4.kobv.de/opus4-bam/frontdoor/index/index/docId/50006>, 2019
- [2] P. -T. Miclea, S. Richter, C. Hagendorf, Three stage size-selective nano- and micro-plastic particle porous membrane filter system for analytical workflows, SETAC Europe, Copenhagen, 15-19.05.2022
- [3] P.-T. Miclea, S. Richter, C. Hagendorf, Nanoporous membrane filter cascade for size-selective analysis of nano- and microplastic particles, Appl.Res., 2022, e202200094
- [4] P. -T. Miclea, K. Altman, Y. Wiesner, C. Hagendorf, Nano and micro plastic particle number and mass-based analysis on a plastic-free size-selective two stage Si membrane filtration cascade, SETAC Europe, Dublin, 01-04.05.2023
- [5] Applications (siliziumfilter.de)

4. Reagent and Equipment

Reagents:

Micro-/Nanoplastic sample
Milli-Q water

Equipment:

Silicon or aluminium oxide filters
Sartorius funnel
Vacuum pump

5. Step-by-step operating procedure

In general, the filtration follows the same procedure independently on the filter used. The pressure of the vacuum pump might be specific. Silicon (Si) membrane filters are less fragile than aluminiumoxide (Al_2O_3) membranes filters.

Note: For reducing the contamination of the samples during filtration couple of precautions must be considered:

1. *Use powder free Nitrile gloves.*
2. *Use lab coat with low content on fibers and avoid wearing clothes with plastic fibers if possible.*
3. *Do not lean over the filtration system during mounting/unmounting or during process.*
4. *Do not use stainless-steel tweezers. Si filter are sensitive to scratches. Al_2O_3 are sensitive to the pressure of the tweezers.*
5. *Do not use any equipment containing plastics or other hydrocarbon-based polymers.*
6. *Use only Teflon covered tweezers.*
7. *IMPORTANT: Filters should be used in the same position as they are delivered, depending on the realization process of the filters the back side can be very rough and the analysis of the samples afterwards difficult.*
8. *Do not come with electric tension in contact. All materials are high conductive.*
9. *Do not let the sample open before or after the experiment.*
10. *Do not throw the samples, brittle and sensitive membrane filters can be damaged.*
11. *When handling particles $<10 \mu m$, please also make sure to use an FFP3 respiratory mask*

5.1 Membrane preparation and equipment assembly

1. Weight the filters used in advance and document the key parameters in Table 1.

- Rinse the filters with Milli-Q water and put the rinsed filters in Milli-Q water in an ultrasonic bath for 5 min.

Note: It is recommended to wet the pores with water before filtration to ensure a good water flow.

Sample_ID	Material	Filter	Filter Poresize [μm]	Date Sampling	Initial weight [mg]	Weheight after sampling [mg]	Material weight [mg]
PR_INCDTL_1	PET	Si	10	01.12.2022			0,00

Table 1. Table Head for sampling

Figure 1. Setup for liquid nano and microplastic experiments. 1-Sartorius funnel, 2- Filtering Duran glass flask in Erlenmeyer form with KECK Montage Set, 3- Vacuum pump

Figure 2. Sample adaptor for cascade filtration for liquid nano and microplastic experiments. 1- Sample holder, 2 - O-ring, 3 - Filter holder, 4 - Screw for filter holder, 5 - Separator for third filter, 6 - End Screw, 7 - Multitool

- For the liquid filtration of nano and microplastic samples the experimental setup is presented in Fig.1 with an adapter shown in Fig.2.

Note: For a simple filtration (one filter) it is necessary to use only components 1-4. For a cascade with 2 filters, all components except 5 are required. For a cascade with 3 different filters, all components are needed.

- Put the multitool [7] in the O-ring [2] as shown in Fig. 4.

Note: In this position the multitool stays vertically and is not necessary to fix with the hand.

5. Inside the filter holder **[3]** in the upper side of the multitool **[7]** and place the desired filter on the multitool **[7]**.
6. Pull the filter holder **[3]** over the multitool **[7]** and screw the O-ring **[2]** with the help of the multitool **[7]** in the filter holder to fix the filter.

Note: Pressing the O-ring too hard against the filter will damage the filter.

7. Put the filter holder **[3]** in the sample holder **[1]** and fix with screw **[4]**.

*Figure 4. Positioning the multitool **[7]** on the O-ring **[2]**.*

8. Separate the Sartorius funnel top part.
9. Put the sample holder **[1]** in the Sartorius funnel (Fig. 5). Insert and fasten the upper part of the Sartorius funnel.

Note: Be sure that the exit part of the sartorius system is closed and the system is correctly vertically aligned to avoid agglomeration of particles on one side of the filter during filtration. For this purpose, it is recommended to use a spirit level.

10. Connect the flask to the vacuum pump.

*Figure 5. Insert the sample holder **[1]** in the Sartorius funnel.*

5.2 Filtration procedures

Example 1: Plastic particles dispersed in solid matrix

1. Put the solid micro-/nanoplastic sample into the filter holder **[3]** on the filter.
2. Add as much Milli-Q water that the filter holder with the sample is filled half. Wait for 4 minutes.
3. Open the valve of the Sartorius funnel and start the vacuum pump. Wait until the water passes the filter.
Note: If more than one micro-/nanoplastic sample should be filters through the same filter, repeat 1-3 for each sample. Start with a stopped vacuum pump.
4. Add another 30 ml of Milli-Q water to the filter holder. Wait until the water passes the filter. Repeat the procedure with another 120 ml of Milli-Q water to guarantee the dissolution of the matrix.
5. Stop the vacuum pump after all water passes the filter.
6. Close the valve of the Sartorius funnel.

Example 2: Plastic particles dispersed in liquid

1. Put the liquid micro-/nanoplastic sample into the filter holder **[3]** on the filter and wait for 2 minutes.
2. Start the vacuum pump and open the valve of the Sartorius funnel. Wait until the water passes the filter.
Note: If the volume of the micro-/nanoplastic sample is high, split the sample and add the rest of the sample or further volume after the liquid passed the filter. Repeat as often as necessary until all sample is filtered.
3. Refill the flask that contained the sample again with 50 ml of Milli-Q water. Stir to get rest of the particles that probably remain in the flask and add the liquid to the Sartorius funnel. Wait until the whole liquid passes the filter.
4. Stop the vacuum pump after all water passes the filter.
5. Close the valve of the Sartorius funnel.

5.3 Filter removal after filtration (except TED-GC/MS)

1. Separate the upper part of the Sartorius funnel and carefully remove the sample holder **[1]** from the Sartorius funnel.
2. Unscrew the screw for filter holder **[4]** without to flip the sample holder and remove the filter holder **[3]** from the sample holder **[1]**.
3. Place the filter holder **[3]** carefully into a glass petri dish.

5.4 Filter preparation for analysis

1. Put the glass petri dish including the filter and filter holder into an oven at 50°C for minimum 4 hours.
2. Unscrew the O-Ring **[2]** using the multitool **[7]** and place it on the table. Fixed the multitool on the O-Ring.
3. Carefully insert the Filter holder **[3]** at the end of the multitool in such a way that the filter remains on the multitool and can be removed using a Teflon tweezer.
4. Weight the dried filter and document the mass in Table 1.

Note: Particles < 10 µm can possibly inhaled. Wear suitable protective equipment.